

**TABIIY MUHOFAZA ETILADIGAN HUDUDLARDA EKOTURIZIMNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI (KITOB GEOLOGIK QO'RIQXONASI
MISOLIDA)**

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Anatatsiya. Maqolada Kitob geologik qo'riqxonasi ekoturizmni rivojlanishining tabiiy-geografik jihatlarini, ayniqsa, iqlimiy va xududiy sharoitlari o'rganib chiqildi va ekoturizmdagi jihatlari xaqida kerakli ma'lumotlar va ilmiy tavsiyalar berildi, Qashqadaryo viloyatida ekoturizmni rivojlanishining tabiiy - geografik jihatlarini, o'rganilib, o'ziga xos tomonlari va imkoniyatlari xaqida ma'lumot berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: Memoriy, yodgorliklar, muzey, iqlim, iqtisodiyoti ekoturizm qo'riqxonasi milliy bog' ekskursiya rekreatsiya.

Abstract. In the article, the natural-geographical aspects of the development of ecotourism of the Kitab geological reserve, especially the climatic and territorial conditions, were studied, and the necessary information and scientific recommendations were given about the aspects of ecotourism.

Keywords: Memorial, monuments, museum, climate, economy, ecotourism, reserve, national park, excursion, recreation.

Аннотация. В статье изучены природно-географические аспекты развития экотуризма Китабского геологического заповедника, особенности климатических и региональных условий, даны необходимые сведения и научные рекомендации по аспектам экотуризма.

Ключевые слова: Мемориал, памятники, музей, климат, экономика, экотуризм, заповедник, национальный парк, экскурсия, рекреация.

Introduction. Kashkadarya region today is one of the richest regions of our country in terms of natural, historical, cultural and socio-economic, tourist and recreational resources, which serve as the basis for the development of almost all types of tourism. One of the main tasks of today is to support the development of tourism activities, increase the efficiency of using the tourism potential of the regions, improve conditions for recreation and tourism, as well as create new jobs in the field of tourism services and increase the employment and well-being of the population. Accordingly, the Decree of the President of our country "On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan" of January 5, 2019[4] has raised to a new level the work on creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism, primarily in the private sector, increasing the competitiveness and quality of services, active and complex promotion of the national tourism product on the world market.

Analysis of thematic literature (Literature review). A large number of scientific studies, including those of scientists from our country and foreign countries, are devoted to scientific and theoretical issues of ecotourism. Sources on ecotourism were first studied at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century in the works of foreign scientists R.Davidov, A.V.Drozdov, V.V.Khrabovchenko, T.V.Bochkaryova, L.I.Egorenkov and A.Taksanov, and in our country by A.N.Nigmatov, N.T.Shamuratova, B.Kamolov, M.Koshimov, S.N.Abduvohidov, Q.S.Yarashev, J.Yu.Hasanov, X.Jumayev, B.Yusupov. However, until now, the Kitab Geological

Reserve has been considered a separate ecotourism site, and its tourism potential has not been studied as a research subject.

Research methodology. We used the scientific and research work of R.Davidov, A.V.Drozdo, V.V.Khrabovchenko, T.V.Bochkaryova, L.I.Egorenkov, A.Taksanov, A.N.Nigmatov, N.T.Shamuratova, B.Kamolov, M.Hoshimov, S.N.Abduvohidov, Q.S.Yarashev, J.Yu.Hasanov and other authors in this field as a methodological basis for the study of the Kitab geological reserve as a reference object of ecotourism.

Analysis and results. It is planned to attract 7 million foreign and 12 million domestic tourists to the country in 2023, which will result in the export of tourism services worth 2 billion dollars this year. In turn, the means of accommodation for tourists will increase due to the commissioning of 170 hotels, 58 hostels, 45 other types of services. [19] It is also planned to build "carvings" in the oriental and modern style along the tourist transport corridor. In particular, in the Kashkadarya region, large-scale work is being carried out to raise tourism to a strategic level, sharply increase the volume of international and domestic tourism, create the necessary conditions for them, improve the quality of tourism services, create additional opportunities for business entities operating in the tourism sector, as well as provide employment for the population and expand their source of income. Today, 48 hotels, 194 guest houses, 16 hostels serve the tourist sector in the region. There are 17 major tourist attractions in the region, which receive more than 700 thousand tourists a year.[20] To the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan of March 8, 2019 No. 198 "On measures to effectively use the tourism potential of Kashkadarya region". Accordingly, the Kashkadarya basin is one of the areas with unique characteristics that are more favorable for the development of ecotourism in the mountainous and mountainous landscapes. Southern Uzbekistan is a region of rich nature, where you can find natural complexes ranging from a shifting sand desert to a dense mountain forest with permafrost.[13] The whole spectrum of landscapes characteristic of the Central Asian plains can be seen in the cool mountainside and high mountain nature. Preserving the nature of this unique region, passing it on to future generations is the responsibility of citizens living in the age of scientific technology and information technology.[12] In the geological history of the republic, the formation of kaleodon, gersin, alpine mountains led to the formation of various sediments, metamorphic mountain rocks. During the Silurian period, the territory of our republic was covered by the sea. Its coast is at the foot of the Gissor Mountains. The Zarafshon and Nurota mountain ranges rose slowly, with large volcanoes erupting in some places.[13] As a result, lava flowed to the surface from the high temperatures, which then cooled and turned into solid rocks, which we can still see with our own eyes in the surroundings of tourist mashups. By explaining the nature of these processes, the guide can generate a lot of interest in the tourists.[10] One such habitat is the Kitab Geological Reserve. It was established in order to protect paleontological and stratigraphic monuments of natural and scientific importance for the geological history of the earth. Paleontological and stratigraphic cuttings of marine sediments from the Yura and Boer periods of the paleozoic soil on the territory of the reserve are its most valuable part.[14] Landscape components are the specific (concrete) environment in which people live, and it is necessary to protect it from any unintended and unwise changes and contamination. When we talk about protecting the landscape, we mean keeping its elements as clean as possible, not allowing its balance to be disturbed, preserving beautiful natural places in their natural state. [7] Landscape and its elements can be protected in a variety of ways, from the total protection of whole parts of a landscape to the preservation of individual and unique landmarks in a landscape.[13] Reserves

are important in protecting all elements of the landscape. [8] Conservation is the highest and most widespread form of nature conservation and recycling. Scientific observations of nature complexes are carried out in nature reserves organized in a certain limited area with characteristic natural landscapes of land, water basin. The primary function of nature preserves is to preserve remarkable, valuable complexes or components of nature for the benefit of society. It is strictly forbidden to engage in any kind of economic activity on the territory of the reserve, as well as the use of nature (plowing, hunting, ploughing, fishing, mushroom gathering).[15] The area around the reserves should be a protected area with limited use. The complexes that exist in the reserves are preserved in their natural state. They serve as a benchmark for the human-dominated and changing neighborhoods.[12] Reserves perform the following functions in nature protection:[17] Protected natural areas (law, 03.12.2004) are divided into the following categories according to the established purpose and regime:

- state reserves;
- complex (landscape) reservations; nature parks;
- state natural monuments;
- territories intended for the preservation, reproduction and restoration of certain natural objects and complexes;
- protected landscapes;
- territories intended for the management of certain natural resources.[17]

1. A sample of all the elements of nature in a particular part of our territory or geographical zone is naturally preserved for future generations.

2. The nature reserve is a well-preserved place, where the laws of development of natural-territorial complexes, their interaction with the organism and the environment can be observed. The relationship between them is a natural laboratory for scientific study.

3. It is concerned with the conservation, reproduction, and protection of plants and animals whose numbers and species are declining.

4. Through nature preserves, natural wonders are presented to the general public and the need for nature conservation is promoted.[14]

Mountain reserves are protected from degradation, pollution, erosion, and erosion of natural complexes that have not been significantly altered by human activity, occupying low, medium, and high mountain slopes.[13] It is also engaged in the conservation and reproduction of flora and fauna, whose names are included in the Red Book. Kitab State Geological Reserve is located in Kitab district of Kashkadarya region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is located in the river basin, on the southwestern edge of the Zarafshon Range. It is located on the north bank of the Kashkadarya (left bank of the Jindiriya) and Karatog, 45 km east of Kitab.[12] The reserve area is 5378 ha, consisting of mountain relief. The absolute heights of the complexes, which were established for the purpose of conservation and planning, as well as nature protection, environmental awareness of the population, are 1300-2650 meters with a relative height of 500 m to 1500 m. The highest point of the reserve is Mount Bursihirmon, with an absolute altitude of 2,061 m. [16] The terrain is mid-mountain, steep-sided, rocky at the top and somewhat flat at the bottom.

The territory of the reserve includes unique mountain ranges and geological formations with their own beauty and landscape, such as Obisafit, Xojaqoorgon, Shahriomon-1, Shahriomon-2, Qorasuv, Zinzilbon, Novobak, Kushnov, Qizilolma, Kula, Jarshafi, Tushlik. Their roots cut deep into the mountain ranges, forming scenic mountain ranges. They are the rocks that allow us to

observe the formation of rocks and the organic forms that become rock. The abundance and diversity of organic remains in this site allows us to determine the age of the reserve beds. The reserve preserves layers of paleozoic soil that were formed under the sea during the period from the Upper Ordovician to the Lower Carboniferous. Among them are numerous fossils of animals and plants that lived in that ancient period [18]. Organic remains preserved in these sections, as monuments of fauna and flora, paleontological and stratigraphic objects of the silurian-ordovician and devonian periods of the geological history of our planet, which occurred 470-330 million years ago, make it possible to compare these sections with those of Central Asia, as well as with those of Western Europe, the Urals, Siberia, China, Canada, Australia and other regions. The Kitab State Geological Reserve was established because of its great scientific significance in the study of earth history. This geological reserve has an international status as one of the most outstanding features of the world's geological heritage due to its importance.[21] "The Kitab State Geological Reserve is famous not only for its hundreds of millions of years old fossils of ancient marine life that have been petrified by climate change, but also for its fauna and flora today. Among the mountain genus of the cuts, the remains of seal-bearing animals were found to belong to 18 groups.

The current flora and fauna of the Book Conservancy is extremely diverse. It is a collection of endemic genera and species that participated in the formation of the mountain semi-savanna. About 800 species of plants have been identified here. In particular, natural walnut groves, pine forests, alpine meadows form a unique forest, and many of the existing endemic species have landscape characteristics. The reserve is home to 19 endemic plant species. 22 of them are included in the Red Book of Uzbekistan.[20] In addition, about 200 species of medicinal plants are found in Uzbekistan, of which about 30 species are widely used in scientific and folk medicine. The animal kingdom includes species of vertebrates and invertebrates. More than 80 species of butterflies have been identified at the reserve, four of which are listed in the Red Book. The wildlife of the Book State Geological Reserve is rich and colorful. There are 168 species of vertebrates, about 15 of which are listed in the Red Book of the Republic of Uzbekistan and are under strict protection. There are also 21 species of mammals, 14 species of reptiles, 2 species of amphibians, and 3 species of fish.[21] In the territory of the reserve, you can find nuts, red apples with high yields, tall trees, wild red poplars and other species of trees.

There are walkways and viewing areas for ecotourists. In the rocks, you can see ancient corals and marine fossils dating back 470 million years. Surprisingly, 140 million years ago, a warm sea basin was located here.[13] The main attraction of the reserve is the opportunity to closely observe the history of the formation of the mountains and the ancient life forms preserved in them.[12] It is also important to note that museums and paleontology museums have a wide range of uses for ecotourism. The main tourist attractions of Kashkadarya are mountains and mountain ranges. Measures have been set for the development of ecological, active, recreational and rural tourism in the territories of Shahrisabz, Kitab, Yakkabog, Kamashi, Dehqonabad districts, as well as cultural and educational tourism with unused opportunities in the sphere.[21] It is envisaged to launch ecotourism products on the foreign market, develop new tourist destinations on natural and historical-cultural attractions, improve the quality of tourist services in the region. Using the opportunities of the portal "Visit Kashkadarya.uz", which will be created as part of a series of marketing activities, the tourist brand of Kashkadarya has been developed. It is planned to build ecotourism programs for visits to the Kenglik station and observatory in Kitab district, as well as the Hisar reserve and the Kitab state geological reserve, a ski base and a suspension road on the territory of the village of Mingchinor. According to forecasts, as a result of

the implementation of this program, the number of foreign tourists visiting Uzbekistan by 2023 is expected to increase by 1.4 times compared to last year and amount to 33.6 thousand people.[20]

The reserve regularly organizes international excursions, scientific conferences in the field of geology and nature protection. In particular, more than 70 scientists from England, Germany, Belgium, Poland, Iran, Spain, the United States, France, the Czech Republic and Russia and other countries participated in the international conference organized on August 25, 2008 with scientific reports on the achievements in the field of geology.[18] They also took part in 8-day geological and ecological marches to get acquainted with the scientific research work carried out in Kitab geological reserve. At the same time, on July 23-25, 2013 a significant amount of work is being done in the field of environmental protection and sustainable development, including the media tour with the participation of a group of journalists organized by the Committee for Environmental Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the Chinor environmental publishing company. [5] As a result of the press conference held in the reserve and the ecotour throughout the region, as well as the acquaintance with the museums, a lot of information about the reserve is given in the local and foreign media.

The book depository owes its name to the mountain slopes that resemble the leaves of a book (Book) in shape. There's also a sculpture created by nature, which is very interesting for ecotourists. You can also see original monuments such as White, Gorilla Child, Area, Sphin and so on. Another attraction of this place is the Hoxha River, a beautiful place with the clearest mountain river, the river has a crossing called "Tushlik". At the bottom of the gap in the wall is a natural rock outline in the shape of the "Darvesh" silhouette, a magical miraculous natural trace.[21] Although the locals named it after one of the explorers, we are reminded of the wonders of nature. The most fascinating country on the planet. In the heart of Europe is Switzerland in the Alps, and the Kitab district, where this reserve is located, is informally described as the "Switzerland of Uzbekistan" because of its extremely saline nature. This definition refers to the unique natural beauty of the Jinnidaryo Valley, which receives water from the Sumsar, Shertog, and Tagimatmon ranges between the Gissor mountain ranges.[12] In order to expand the possibilities of ecotourism, in recent times, in order to further improve the ecotourism potential of Kitab Geological Reserve, a decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan was announced in the field of transforming it into "Kitob Geology National Nature Park". In accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of June 30, 2020 No PQ-4766 "On the creation of Kitab geological national nature park in the form of a state nature protection institution" and the instructions set forth in the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of September 2, 2020, it is recommended to establish Kitab geological national nature park in the form of a state nature protection institution on the basis of Kitab state geological reserve in Kitab district of Kashkadarya region.[5] In order to ensure the execution of this resolution. Today, local and international experts are working together to achieve these goals.

According to the document measures have been taken to further strengthen the role and position of the unique natural monuments formed over the centuries and the internationally recognized Devonian cut of Zinzilban in geological science on the territory of the state institution Kitab State Geological Reserve of the State Committee on Geology and Mineral Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan. [16] The National Park attaches great importance to the preservation and improvement of natural complexes for the recreation of the population, in which all facilities are built for a large number of tourists, athletes, vacationers. But natural resources require special care for the fauna and flora. The reason for the name "National Park" is that the territory and the service

area that serves it are under control, and all social infrastructure is specially provided by the state. National parks preserve beautiful landscapes rich in fauna and flora that have been little altered by humans.[12] Access to national parks and short-term recreation is aimed at expanding knowledge about nature. National parks began to be created in a number of foreign countries at the end of the last century and the beginning of this century. The phrase "national park" originated in the 19th century in the United States as a designation for protected natural areas (Yellowstone Park in 1872). Yellowstone National Park is a national park in the U.S. state of North Carolina.[21] The park encompasses 9,000 square miles and features more than 3,000 geysers and hot springs, as well as the giant Yellowstone River waterfalls. The main feature of their organization is the free access of people to rare natural objects and at the same time the prohibition of their use for ordinary economic purposes.

The difference between a national park and a nature reserve is that only tourism is allowed in a national park, and all other activities are prohibited. The first national parks in Canada were established in the Rocky Mountains in 1885. By the beginning of the 20th century, national parks had been established on every continent except Antarctica and in most countries of the world. Kafue, the largest national park in Africa, is located in Zambia. Its area is 2 million 250 thousand hectares. The largest national parks in Asia are in India (Tirap), Malaysia (Taman Negara), Japan (Daysepudzan), and other countries.[9] In South America, national parks are located in mountainous forested areas that are difficult to access. It's important to note that many of the parks around the world, when they were first created, were primarily designed to protect nature, and they play a big role in that. For example, the Budd-Buffalo National Park in Canada has played a major role in the conservation and reproduction of the species. In recent years, however, the use of national parks for ecotourism and recreation has expanded.[15] In national parks, visitors can enjoy all types of services, which ensures that the protected areas are of high value.[21] Ecotourism is a form of tourism in which more profits are generated by spending less money than other forms of tourism.[16] So it's much more cost-effective. The use of certain areas for ecotourism brings Western countries, at times, a higher return on its resources than any other sector. For example, the revenue generated by tourists and recreational visitors to California's state and national parks is \$210 million a year.

Foreign experience has shown that the overuse and inefficient use of these parks can have negative consequences. It should be recognized that the effective use of national parks with proper organization of work will lead to a sharp increase in the flow of domestic and foreign tourists.[9] Based on the experience of foreign countries, work is being carried out to develop and implement measures to improve the activities of national nature parks established on the territory of our country's Gorakchans, as it is appropriate to focus on the activities of Kitab geological national nature park located in the Kashkadarya basin.[20] In particular, attention is paid to the issues of further increasing the economic potential of geotourism and ecotourism in this region.[14] The resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to improve the activities of the Kitab geological national nature park was announced. According to him, the total area of Kitab Geology National Nature Park is 3938 hectares, of which. [5] The protected area is 2221 hectares, the area used for recreational purposes is 400 hectares, and the area used for economic purposes is 1317 hectares. In addition to the above, the measures include the use of the road leading to the Zinzilban crossing as a new ecotourism destination, the preparation and promotion of dissemination materials highlighting the ecotourism potential of the region. It is also aimed at increasing the number of domestic and foreign tourists visiting the region and increasing

the economic and social potential of the region, based on the recommendations of UNESCO to include it in the Global Geoparks Network in the future.[14] Significantly, the Kitab Geology National Park has the potential to be included in the UNESCO Global Geoparks Network. It should be noted that the territory of Kitab Geological National Nature Park has the most basic requirements for international geoparks.

It identifies several existing geological and natural features in conjunction with the Global Stratotype Boundary Point (GSSP) Few people know that the Book Region is a unique place where life emerged from the oceans to the land.[18] The Zinzibans have the unique reference status in the world. In simple terms, there are a few geological sites like this in the world, but it's the Book Division that is recognized as the benchmark by the international community. What's unique about it is that it's a unified geologic crust, meaning that every time period can be accurately tracked. This means that the fossil record allows us to trace marine plants and animals that lived 400 million years ago. The Kitab State Geological National Park is of interest not only to geologists and paleontologists, but also to ecotourism and extreme sports enthusiasts.[8] Imagine being able to not only see the temporary curves of the Zanzibar section, but to feel, to think about life. It turns out that there was a sea here 400 million years ago. Over time, the grains of sand sink and are crushed.

Then the sea moved, and dry land appeared instead. Interestingly, these geological deposits were once horizontal, but have become vertical due to climate change.[11] That's why it's so exciting to study these slopes. The Kitab Geological Reserve is very important in its position, it was originally established to protect rare products and objects of nature. Jauz Mountain with a total length of 55 meters and Khojaqoon Mountain with a length of 43 meters were studied by geologist Abdulla Mamatov in 1965 within the territory of the Kitab Geological Reserve. The Jauz and Khojaqoon caves are one of the most interesting types of ecotourism.[12] However, to give a brief information about the museum of the museum, it is necessary to travel 60-65 km from the city of Shahrissabz to the place where the museum is located. This distance is a very interesting route for ecotourists. While traveling along the high hills on both coasts of Jinnidaria, the thick woodlands, especially as you pass the village of Jaus, you are convinced that the traditions, the way of life of the people, the ancient paintings, the legends, the architecture of ancient Turkistan are part of the pure and unchanged until now. It is decorated with a flowery, spiky flowery wood. Seeing the centuries-old Chinars in this village, as well as the houses of the local people with their unique architecture, is of great interest to everyone. The main part of the village is occupied by houses with a flat roof of clay, typical of ancient Muslim architecture, the front part is decorated with carved columns. Because these houses were built on slopes, often the roof of the first served as a courtyard for the second, and from a distance these buildings resembled multi-story houses.[16] If you look at the furniture in the courtyards, you'll notice that many of them have been in use since ancient times, including pots and pans, ancient urchins, oil cups, and old pots on the walls.

This rule is broken by a few new houses built in the current style at the entrance to the village, with a thatched roof. These are houses that were moved from the outskirts of the village after the riots. According to local residents, the village is around 1,600 to 1,900 years old, and it stretches for three kilometers along the right bank of the Jinnidaria. Among the museum's rare and valuable exhibits are dinosaur footprints. They lived in the Carboniferous and Lower Ordovician periods. The footprints in the museum are of a Carnivorous predatory dinosaur, traced to its claws. Decisions of the Council of Ministers include plans on the issues of accelerated introduction of

modern technologies and expansion of Internet services [6]. On this basis, the project on the development of the museum should develop a 3D galagram of these exhibits. The Galagramma is placed along the hall where the dinosaur footprints are stored, allowing the carnivorous, stichosaurian, and other dinosaur figures to move freely throughout the hall. In order to develop museum tourism, in the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan on the approval of the Program of Measures for Improving the Activity of State Museums and Strengthening the Material-Technical Base in 2017-2027, it was decided to create 3D and audio formats of 2,000 rare museum objects in 6 languages through the implementation of the Virtual Museum Project; to update the websites of state museums, create a mobile electronic application and integrate them into a single portal, ensure the maintenance of tourism-oriented museum sites in 6 foreign languages[17] Taking into account this, the further improvement of the museum site of Kitab Geological Reserve is one of the most important issues. At the same time, in order to create convenience for visitors to the museum, a plan is being developed for the creation of a special place for children and the organization of excursions according to the age and type (area) of the audience.

Concluding. Based on the foregoing, we can draw the following conclusions. Since the independence of Uzbekistan, work on preservation and protection of natural conditions in Uzbekistan has been intensified. This is due, first of all, to the correct conduct of Uzbekistan's state policy, and secondly, to the ancient appreciation of nature by the Uzbek people living in our country. This is reflected even in the customs and traditions of our people. After gaining independence, Uzbekistan began to accelerate the work on conservation and effective use of nature. The Kitab geological reserve is important in the protection of mountain landscapes, which can be used as an important natural object of ecological tourism and recreation, as well as carrying out scientific research in the field of earth sciences, studying landscapes and individual components of landscapes. At present, in many countries, including Uzbekistan, serious attention is paid to the creation of reserves and national parks, expanding their area. From this perspective, today the day is organized as a necessity of the times and a social necessity to preserve nature and increase the efficiency of ecotourism processes.

The presidential decree on the establishment of the National Park of Kitab Geology and the measures developed by the Cabinet of Ministers as its execution made it possible to turn it into a base for the development of domestic and foreign tourism in the future. These works, in turn, will become the basis for the educational practice organized for students and students from the recreation area of the National Natural Park of Kitab Geology. As a result, theoretical knowledge is directly linked to practical knowledge. As a result, the combination of theoretical and practical knowledge ensures that the knowledge acquired in the field of geography and ecotourism is strong. The creation of the Kitab Geology National Nature Park is aimed at implementing measures aimed at protecting nature, organizing scientific research and employing the local population, not only self-sufficient, using some parts of the national park for ecotourism purposes.

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